

DESORPTION OF LEAD (II), CADMIUM (II) AND ZINC (II) ADSORBED BY GEORGIAN NATURAL MORDENITE

*Akhalbedashvili L.,
Gagniashvili N.*

Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University, Caucasian Institute of Mineral Resources, Tbilisi, Georgia

ABSTRACT

With the increase of pollutants, adsorbents are actively used to remove them from the environment. The effectiveness of the adsorbent is determined not only by how well it can absorb metal but also by its ability to regenerate and reuse.

The study examines the desorption characteristics of natural zeolite Mordenite in relation to lead, zinc and cadmium ions, previously adsorbed in static mode. Desorption was carried out with different chemical reagents, such as CH₃COOH, HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄ and EDTA. The results show that the extent of desorption depends on the nature of the metal and the desorbing agent. EDTA has the best results for desorption. It takes out 90.49% of adsorbed lead, Zn-97.47%, and Cd-85.59%, respectively. The research results also clearly show that the use of inorganic acids gives much more effective results compared with organic ones.

Keywords: Desorption, regeneration, Mordenite, heavy metals.

Introduction

In the practice of treating wastewater from heavy metal ions, sorption technologies are increasingly used. The advantages of the adsorption process are ease of operation and availability (Rathi & Kumar, 2021). An important indicator of the sorption process is the possibility of selective extraction of components - pollutants from industrial solutions. Therefore, the use of sorption methods with selective research and the study of ongoing processes seems to be a relevant area of research. An equally important factor is the study of desorption of metal ions without destruction of the sorbent, which is of practical and scientific interest.

A necessary element of any technological scheme for adsorption wastewater treatment is the regeneration of the sorbent after its saturation with substances extracted from wastewater. There are several methods of regeneration sorbents: extraction with organic solvents, low-temperature and high-temperature regeneration, biochemical and chemical regeneration.

The state of adsorbed heavy metal ions, the degree of their connection with the components of the adsorbents, possibility of complex formation and penetration into these complex polydisperse systems have not yet been sufficiently studied.

Natural zeolites are noteworthy among low-cost effective adsorbents. So, Georgian natural mordenite has also been successfully used as adsorbent to remove heavy metals from water (Gagniashvili & Akhalbedashvili, 2023). HM, adsorbed by zeolites, may be successfully removed by desorption with different agents of acid or alkali nature to one degree or another, which plays very important role in the total process of cleaning. For a better prediction of mordenite performance, it is important to desorb adsorbed heavy metals and reuse them in as many cycles as possible. Desorption processes depend on various parameters such as selectivity and structural features of adsorbents, solution type and concentration. It is important to determine how often the zeolite can be regenerated, which largely depends on the nature of the zeolite and heavy metal ions. The desorption process can be useful to determine the adsorption mechanism. It shows whether the adsorption process can be reversible at equilibrium by comparing

the rates of adsorption and desorption processes (Fu & Wang, 2011).

Experimental part

The Georgian natural mordenite sample used in the adsorption experiment, on which 0.74 mg/g of Zn, 0.39 mg/g of Cd and 2.48 mg/g of Pb were adsorbed, was carefully washed with distilled water and dried in an oven at 105 °C for 12 hours. The zeolite was then placed in a solution of different desorbing agents: 1M CH₃COOH, 1M HCl, 0.2 M HNO₃, 0.2M H₂SO₄ and 0.2 M EDTA. Mordenite samples contaminated with lead, zinc and cadmium ions were placed in the appropriate desorbent solution at room temperature. The solution was stirred continuously at 25 °C until equilibrium was reached (24 hours). The solutions were filtered at regular intervals and the content of heavy metals was determined on an atomic absorption spectrometer (AAnalyst 200 of firm "Perkin Elmer").

The amount of each metal transferred from the zeolite to the solution per unit mass of adsorbent (q_d (mg/g)) at equilibrium is calculated by the formula:

$$q_d = \frac{(C_{desorbed}) \cdot V}{m}$$

where: $C_{desorbed}$ is the metal concentration in the liquid phase that is in the desorbing solution at the end of the desorption process (under equilibrium conditions) (mg/L), V is the volume of the desorbing solution, m is the mass of the desorbent (Katsou et al., 2011).

The percentage content of desorbed metals is calculated by the formula:

$$\% \text{ desorption} = \frac{q_d}{q_e} \times 100\%$$

where, q_d is the amount of desorbed metal per unit mass (mg/g), and q_e is the amount of metal adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent at equilibrium (mg/g).

Result and discussion

In selecting an effective adsorbent, it is important that it has not only good adsorption capacity but also good desorption ability with regard to heavy metals for multiple uses of adsorbent. Therefore, it was necessary to investigate the desorption capacity of used natural mordenite for lead (II), cadmium (II) and zinc (II) ions. It is important that the selected desorbing substance would be highly effective and would not cause damage to the adsorbent. For this purpose, several desorbents were selected: 0.2M EDTA as a strong complexing

agent, 1M HCl, 0.2 M HNO₃ and 0.2M H₂SO₄ from strong inorganic, and 1M CH₃COOH from organic acids.

To select the optimal desorbing solution, successive regeneration studies were performed. Desorption of lead (II), cadmium (II) and zinc (II) ions from zeolite was studied using 5 above-mentioned desorbing solutions. Figures 1, 2, and 3 show the time dependence of the desorption of lead (II), cadmium (II), and zinc (II) ions and the desorption efficiency in %. Desorption of lead (II), using EDTA, hydrochloric and nitric acids is stepwise (Fig. 1); desorption of cadmium (II), and practically zinc (II) occurs stepwise by all acids except acetic one (Fig. 2 and 3). Presumably, at the first stage of desorption, cation-exchange forms of heavy metals weakly fixed in the zeolite channels are extracted. Then the proportion of mobile forms of heavy metals increases sharply, and at the last stage, heavy metals, more tightly bound to the framework and hydroxyl groups are desorbed.

The results collected from the desorption study (table 1), which shows that the efficiency of metal regeneration depends both on the nature of the desorbing solution and the metal. The results show that 0.2 M EDTA has the highest degree of desorption for all three metals: 90.49% for lead, 85.59% for cadmium and 97.47% for zinc. A comparison of inorganic acids shows that the efficiency of all three acids is higher than 60% in the case of zinc and cadmium. And the degree of desorption of lead is very low in the case of sulfuric acid. This is probably related to the formation of lead sulfate precipitation, which occupies and passivates the active centers of adsorption. M²⁺ and H⁺ are easily exchanged, which means that lead (II), cadmium (II) and zinc (II) ions can be recovered with inorganic acids (Shukla et al., 2002). The use of EDTA solution is effective for the recovery of metals adsorbed on mor-denite due to the high value of conditional complex formation (Deng et al., 2007).

Figure. 1 Amount of lead desorbed from Mordenite versus the time using desorbing solutions: 1M CH₃COOH, 1M HCl, 0.2 M HNO₃, 0.2M H₂SO₄ and 0,2 M EDTA respectively.

Figure. 2 Amount of Cd(II) desorbed from Mordenite versus the time using desorbing solutions: 1M CH₃COOH, 1M HCl, 0.2 M HNO₃, 0.2M H₂SO₄ and 0,2 M EDTA respectively

Figure. 3 Amount of Zn(II) desorbed from Mordenite versus the time using desorbing solutions: 1M CH₃COOH, 1M HCl, 0.2 M HNO₃, 0.2M H₂SO₄ and 0,2 M EDTA respectively

Table 1.

Pb(II), Cd(II) and Zn(II) recovery by different desorbing solution				
Desorbing agent	Concentration at the moment of desorption equilibrium (mg/l)	Desorption capacity (mg/g)	Desorption efficiency %	
Zn	HCl	1.80	0.72	97.51
	H ₂ SO ₄	1.59	0.64	86.30
	HNO ₃	1.46	0.58	79.21
	EDTA	1.42	0.57	97.47
	CH ₃ COOH	1.02	0.41	55.49
Pb	HCl	16.21	1.62	65.40
	H ₂ SO ₄	2.15	0.21	8.67
	HNO ₃	13.12	1.31	52.93
	EDTA	22.43	2.24	90.49
	CH ₃ COOH	1.35	1.35	5.44
Cd	HCl	2.69	0.27	68.45
	H ₂ SO ₄	2.52	0.25	64.17
	HNO ₃	3.15	0.31	80.28
	EDTA	3.36	0.33	85.59
	CH ₃ COOH	0.69	0.069	17.55

The results show that it is better to use mineral acids as adsorbent agents, compared to organic ones. Generally, organic acids have a low degree of dissociation and less quality of H⁺, than inorganic acids. And, the insufficient amount of H⁺ generated, cannot remove heavy metal cations from the surface of mordenite completely.

The results of our research are very important because they will help to select the right desorbing material. The high desorption rate for all three metals indicates the effectiveness of the adsorbent.

Conclusions

To evaluate the efficiency of the adsorbent, regeneration of the adsorbent containing lead, cadmium and zinc cations was carried out. As a result of the research, it was determined that the nature of the metal affects

the selection of the desorbing solution. The results show that the desorption efficiency is higher for EDTA and inorganic acid than for acetic acid. Desorption occurs in steps as the proportion of various HM complexes, existing in the zeolite voids increases. Presumably, at the first stage of desorption, cation-exchange forms of metals, weakly bound in the zeolite channels are extracted. Then desorption of mobile forms of HMs sharply increases, and at the last stage, clusters of heavy metals with hydroxyl groups and other metal-binding centers of the zeolite framework are destroyed.

Overall, the use of EDTA and inorganic acids for desorption is a promising way to regenerate mordenite contaminated with lead, cadmium and zinc ions.

The high desorption rate for all three metals indicates the effectiveness of the adsorbent.

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